

New types of generalizations of θ -closed sets

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Abstract

The aim of this paper is to introduce and study the class of T -closed sets as a generalization of θ -closed sets, which is properly placed between θ -closed sets and closed sets. A generalization of T -closed sets, namely, generalized T -closed sets is introduced and studied, which is properly placed between T -closed sets and g -closed sets.

Keywords: T -closed sets; generalized T -closed sets; θ -closed sets.

1. INTRODUCTION

In 1968, N. V. Veličko [1] introduced the definition of θ -closed sets via θ -closure operator. In 1970, Norman Levine [3] introduced a generalization of closed sets and studied their basic properties. In 1982, W. Dunham [4] introduced a new closure operator based on g -closed sets. In 1999, J. Dontchev and H. Maki [2] introduced a generalization of θ -closed sets, namely, θ -generalized closed sets. In this paper, we introduce a generalization of θ -closed sets called T -closed sets via T -closure operator which is based on Dunham's closure operator, also we introduce a generalization of T -closed sets which is stronger than g -closed sets.

2. PRELIMINARIES

Throughout this paper (X, τ) , (Y, σ) and (Z, η) (briefly, X , Y and Z) represent topological spaces on which no separation axioms are assumed unless otherwise stated. For a subset A of a topological space (X, τ) , $\text{cl}(A)$ and $\text{int}(A)$ denote the closure and the interior of A , respectively.

We recall the following definitions, which are useful in the sequel.

Definition 2.1 A subset A of a space (X, τ) is called.

- (1) θ -closed [1] if $A = \text{cl}_\theta(A)$, Where $\text{cl}_\theta(A) = \{x \in X: \text{cl}(U) \cap A \neq \emptyset, \forall U \in \tau, x \in U\}$.
- (2) generalized closed (briefly, g -closed) [3] if $\text{cl}(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is open.
- (3) θ -generalized closed (briefly, θ - g -closed) [2] if $\text{cl}_\theta(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is open.
- (4) semi-generalized closed (briefly, sg -closed) [7] if $\text{cl}_s(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is semi-open.
- (5) generalized α -closed (briefly, $g\alpha$ -closed) [8] if $\text{cl}_\alpha(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is α -open.

- (6) generalized semi-closed (briefly, gs-closed) [9] if $cl_s(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is open.
- (7) α -generalized closed (briefly, α g-closed) [10] if $cl_\alpha(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is open.
- (8) generalized semi-preclosed (briefly, gsp-closed) [11] if $cl_{sp}(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is open.
- (9) regular generalized closed (rg-closed) [12] if $cl(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is regular-open.
- (10) α -closed [13] if $cl(int(cl(A))) \subseteq A$. The intersection of all α -closed sets containing A is called α -closure [16] and is denoted by $cl_\alpha(A)$.
- (11) semi-closed [14] if $int(cl(A)) \subseteq A$. The intersection of all semi-closed sets containing A is called semi-closure [17] and is denoted by $cl_s(A)$.
- (12) semi-preclosed [15] if $int(cl(int(A))) \subseteq A$. The intersection of all semi-preclosed sets containing A is called semipre-closure [15] and is denoted by $cl_{sp}(A)$.
- (13) regular open [23] if $A = int(cl(A))$.

Definition 2.2 [4] For a subset A of a topological space (X, τ) , $cl^*(A) = \bigcap \{F: A \subseteq F, F \text{ is } g\text{-closed}\}$.

Lemma 2.1 [4] If $A \subseteq X$, then $A \subseteq cl^*(A) \subseteq cl(A)$.

Definition 2.3 [6] In a space X , A is equivalent to B (written $A \equiv B$) iff for each open set U , $A \subseteq U$ iff $B \subseteq U$.

Definition 2.4 [3] A topological space X is called $T_{1/2}$ -space iff every g -closed set is closed.

Theorem 2.1 [22] X is $T_{1/2}$ -space iff for each $x \in X$, either $\{x\}$ is open or $\{x\}$ is closed.

3. T-CLOSED SETS

In this section, we introduce a new class of sets, namely, T-closed sets as a generalization of θ -closed sets and study their fundamental properties.

Definition 3.1 A subset A of a topological space X is called T-closed set if $A = cl_T(A)$, where $cl_T(A) = \{x \in X: cl^*(U) \cap A \neq \emptyset, \forall U \in \tau \text{ and } x \in U\}$. The complement of a T-closed set is called T-open set. The family of all T-closed (resp. T-open) sets is denoted by $TC(X)$ (resp. $TO(X)$).

Proposition 3.1 For a subset $A \subseteq X$, $A \subseteq cl_T(A)$.

Proof: Let $x \in A$. Then for every open set U containing x , we have $cl^*(U) \cap A \neq \emptyset$ which means that $x \in cl_T(A)$. Hence $A \subseteq cl_T(A)$.

Definition 3.2 A subset A of a topological space X is called T-open set if $A = int_T(A)$, where $int_T(A) = \{x \in X: cl^*(U) \subseteq A, U \in \tau \text{ and } x \in U\}$.

Proposition 3.2 For a subset $A \subseteq X$, $int_T(A) \subseteq A$.

Proof: Let $x \in int_T(A)$, then there exists an open set U containing x such that $cl^*(U) \subseteq A$ and since $U \subseteq cl^*(U)$, we have $x \in A$. Thus $int_T(A) \subseteq A$.

Proposition 3.3 $int_T(A) = \bigcup \{U \in \tau: cl^*(U) \subseteq A\}$.

Proof: Let $x \in \text{int}_{\mathcal{T}}(A)$, then there exists an open set U containing x such that $\text{cl}^*(U) \subseteq A$ and then $x \in \cup \{U \in \tau: \text{cl}^*(U) \subseteq A\}$. Thus $\text{int}_{\mathcal{T}}(A) \subseteq \cup \{U \in \tau: \text{cl}^*(U) \subseteq A\}$. Conversely, let $x \in \cup \{U \in \tau: \text{cl}^*(U) \subseteq A\}$, then there exists an open set U containing x such that $\text{cl}^*(U) \subseteq A$ and then $x \in \text{int}_{\mathcal{T}}(A)$. Therefore, $\cup \{U \in \tau: \text{cl}^*(U) \subseteq A\} \subseteq \text{int}_{\mathcal{T}}(A)$ and hence $\text{int}_{\mathcal{T}}(A) = \cup \{U \in \tau: \text{cl}^*(U) \subseteq A\}$.

We give an example of \mathcal{T} -closed sets.

Example 3.1 $X = \{a, b, c\}$, $\tau = \{X, \varnothing, \{a\}\}$. $\mathcal{T}C(X) = \{X, \varnothing, \{b, c\}\}$.

Proposition 3.4 For a subset A of a topological space X , $\text{cl}_{\mathcal{T}}(A) \subseteq \text{cl}_{\theta}(A)$.

Proof: Let $x \in \text{cl}_{\mathcal{T}}(A)$, then for every open U containing x $\text{cl}^*(U) \cap A \neq \varnothing$. But $\text{cl}^*(U) \subseteq \text{cl}(U)$. Therefore, $\text{cl}(U) \cap A \neq \varnothing$. Thus $x \in \text{cl}_{\theta}(A)$.

Proposition 3.5 For a subset A of a topological space X , $\text{cl}(A) \subseteq \text{cl}_{\mathcal{T}}(A)$.

Proof: Let $x \in \text{cl}(A)$, then for every open set U containing x $U \cap A \neq \varnothing$. Then $\text{cl}^*(U) \cap A \neq \varnothing$ and hence $x \in \text{cl}_{\mathcal{T}}(A)$. Thus $\text{cl}(A) \subseteq \text{cl}_{\mathcal{T}}(A)$.

Proposition 3.6 Every θ -closed set is \mathcal{T} -closed.

Proof: Let A be θ -closed set. Then $A = \text{cl}_{\theta}(A)$, and we have $\text{cl}_{\theta}(A) = A \subseteq \text{cl}_{\mathcal{T}}(A)$. Thus $A = \text{cl}_{\mathcal{T}}(A)$ and hence A is \mathcal{T} -closed set.

Proposition 3.7 Every \mathcal{T} -closed set is closed.

Proof: Let A be \mathcal{T} -closed set. Then $A = \text{cl}_{\mathcal{T}}(A)$. We want to show that $\text{cl}(A) = A = \text{cl}_{\mathcal{T}}(A)$. We know that $\text{cl}(A) \subseteq \text{cl}_{\mathcal{T}}(A) = A$. Therefore $A = \text{cl}(A)$ and hence A is closed.

We have the following implications.

Figure (1)

Implications in the previous Fig. can't be reversed as shown from the following examples.

Example 3.2 Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$, $\tau = \{X, \varnothing, \{a\}\}$, $\{b, c\}$ is \mathcal{T} -closed but not θ -closed.

Example 3.3 Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$, $\tau = \{X, \varnothing, \{a, c\}\}$, $\{b\}$ is closed but not \mathcal{T} -closed.

Proposition 3.8 For two subsets A, B of a topological space X , if $A \subseteq B$, then $\text{cl}_{\mathcal{T}}(A) \subseteq \text{cl}_{\mathcal{T}}(B)$.

Proof: Let $x \in \text{cl}_{\mathcal{T}}(A)$, then for every U open containing x , $\text{cl}^*(U) \cap A \neq \varnothing$. But, $A \subseteq B$ then, $\text{cl}^*(U) \cap B \neq \varnothing$. Thus $x \in \text{cl}_{\mathcal{T}}(B)$ and therefore, $\text{cl}_{\mathcal{T}}(A) \subseteq \text{cl}_{\mathcal{T}}(B)$.

Proposition 3.9 For two subsets A, B of a topological space X , $\text{cl}_{\mathcal{T}}(A \cup B) = \text{cl}_{\mathcal{T}}(A) \cup \text{cl}_{\mathcal{T}}(B)$.

Proof: $A \subseteq A \cup B$ then, $\text{cl}_{\mathcal{T}}(A) \subseteq \text{cl}_{\mathcal{T}}(A \cup B)$. Similarly, $\text{cl}_{\mathcal{T}}(B) \subseteq \text{cl}_{\mathcal{T}}(A \cup B)$ and then, $\text{cl}_{\mathcal{T}}(A) \cup \text{cl}_{\mathcal{T}}(B) \subseteq \text{cl}_{\mathcal{T}}(A \cup B)$. Now, we want to show that $\text{cl}_{\mathcal{T}}(A \cup B) \subseteq \text{cl}_{\mathcal{T}}(A) \cup \text{cl}_{\mathcal{T}}(B)$. Let $x \notin \text{cl}_{\mathcal{T}}(A) \cup \text{cl}_{\mathcal{T}}(B)$ which leads to

$cl^*(U) \cap A = \emptyset$, $cl^*(U) \cap B = \emptyset$ for every open set U containing x and therefore, $cl^*(U) \cap (A \cup B) = \emptyset$ for every open set U containing x . Thus, $cl_{\mathcal{T}}(A \cup B) \subseteq cl_{\mathcal{T}}(A) \cup cl_{\mathcal{T}}(B)$ and hence, $cl_{\mathcal{T}}(A \cup B) = cl_{\mathcal{T}}(A) \cup cl_{\mathcal{T}}(B)$.

Proposition 3.10 For two subsets A, B of a topological space X , $cl_{\mathcal{T}}(A \cap B) \subseteq cl_{\mathcal{T}}(A) \cap cl_{\mathcal{T}}(B)$.

Proof: Let $x \in cl_{\mathcal{T}}(A \cap B)$ then, $cl^*(U) \cap (A \cap B) \neq \emptyset$ for every open set U containing x . Therefore, $cl^*(U) \cap A \neq \emptyset$, $cl^*(U) \cap B \neq \emptyset$ for every open set U containing x . Thus, $x \in cl_{\mathcal{T}}(A) \cap cl_{\mathcal{T}}(B)$ and therefore, $cl_{\mathcal{T}}(A \cap B) \subseteq cl_{\mathcal{T}}(A) \cap cl_{\mathcal{T}}(B)$.

Inclusion can't be replaced by equality in the previous proposition as shown from the following example.

Example 3.4 Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$, $\tau = \{X, \emptyset, \{a, b\}, \{b, c\}, \{b\}, \{a, b, c\}\}$. Let $A = \{a, c\}$, $B = \{b, c\}$ and we have, $cl_{\mathcal{T}}(A) = \{a, c, d\}$, $cl_{\mathcal{T}}(B) = X$. But, $cl_{\mathcal{T}}(A \cap B) = cl_{\mathcal{T}}(\{c\}) = \{c, d\} \neq \{a, c, d\} = cl_{\mathcal{T}}(A) \cap cl_{\mathcal{T}}(B)$.

Proposition 3.11 The union of two \mathcal{T} -closed sets, is \mathcal{T} -closed.

Proof: Let A, B be \mathcal{T} -closed sets. We want to show that $cl_{\mathcal{T}}(A \cup B) = A \cup B$. $cl_{\mathcal{T}}(A \cup B) = cl_{\mathcal{T}}(A) \cup cl_{\mathcal{T}}(B) = A \cup B$ and therefore, $A \cup B$ is \mathcal{T} -closed set.

Proposition 3.12 The intersection of two \mathcal{T} -closed sets, is \mathcal{T} -closed.

Proof: Let A, B be \mathcal{T} -closed sets. We want to show that $cl_{\mathcal{T}}(A \cap B) = A \cap B$. We have, $A \cap B \subseteq cl_{\mathcal{T}}(A \cap B)$ and $cl_{\mathcal{T}}(A \cap B) \subseteq cl_{\mathcal{T}}(A) \cap cl_{\mathcal{T}}(B) = A \cap B$. Thus, $cl_{\mathcal{T}}(A \cap B) = A \cap B$.

4. GENERALIZED \mathcal{T} -CLOSED SETS

In this section, we introduce a generalization of sets which introduced in section 3 and study their basic properties.

Definition 4.1 A subset A of a topological space X is called generalized \mathcal{T} -closed set (briefly, $g\mathcal{T}$ -closed) if $cl_{\mathcal{T}}(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is open. The complement of $g\mathcal{T}$ -closed set is called $g\mathcal{T}$ -open.

The family of all $g\mathcal{T}$ -closed (resp. $g\mathcal{T}$ -open) sets is denoted by $G\mathcal{T}C(X)$ (resp. $G\mathcal{T}O(X)$).

Lemma 4.1 For a subset A of a topological space X , $(cl_{\mathcal{T}}(A))^c = int_{\mathcal{T}}(A^c)$.

Proof. Let $x \in (cl_{\mathcal{T}}(A))^c$ which means that $x \notin cl_{\mathcal{T}}(A)$. Then, there exists at least one open set U containing x such that $cl^*(U) \cap A = \emptyset$ which implies $cl^*(U) \subseteq A^c$. Thus, $x \in int_{\mathcal{T}}(A^c)$ and therefore, $(cl_{\mathcal{T}}(A))^c \subseteq int_{\mathcal{T}}(A^c)$. Now, we want to show that $int_{\mathcal{T}}(A^c) \subseteq (cl_{\mathcal{T}}(A))^c$. Let $x \in int_{\mathcal{T}}(A^c)$ which means that $x \in A^c$. Then, for every open set U containing x , we have $cl^*(U) \cap A = \emptyset$. Thus $x \notin cl_{\mathcal{T}}(A)$ and therefore $int_{\mathcal{T}}(A^c) \subseteq (cl_{\mathcal{T}}(A))^c$. Hence $(cl_{\mathcal{T}}(A))^c = int_{\mathcal{T}}(A^c)$.

Proposition 4.1 A subset A of a topological space X is generalized \mathcal{T} -open (briefly, $g\mathcal{T}$ -open) iff $F \subseteq int_{\mathcal{T}}(A)$ whenever $F \subseteq A$ and F is closed.

Proof. Let A be a $g\mathcal{T}$ -open set and $F \subseteq A$ where F is closed. Then, $A^c \subseteq F^c = U$, and since U is open and A^c is $g\mathcal{T}$ -closed and from lemma 4.1 we have, $cl_{\mathcal{T}}(A^c) \subseteq U$ and $F \subseteq (cl_{\mathcal{T}}(A^c))^c = int_{\mathcal{T}}(A)$. Conversely, Let $A^c \subseteq U$ where U is open, then $F = U^c \subseteq A$ and from the assumption we have, $F \subseteq int_{\mathcal{T}}(A)$ and from lemma 4.1 $(int_{\mathcal{T}}(A))^c = cl_{\mathcal{T}}(A^c) \subseteq U$. Thus A^c is $g\mathcal{T}$ -closed set and hence, A is $g\mathcal{T}$ -open.

Proposition 4.2 Every \mathcal{T} -closed set is $g\mathcal{T}$ -closed set.

Proof: Let A be a T -closed set and $A \subseteq U$, U open. Then, $cl_{\mathcal{T}}(A) = A \subseteq U$ and therefore A is gT -closed set.

The converse of the previous proposition is not true in general as shown from the following example.

Example 4.1 Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$, $\tau = \{X, \emptyset, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{b, c\}, \{a, c\}\}$. We can see that $\{a, b\}$ is gT -closed set but not T -closed set.

Proposition 4.3 Every gT -closed set is g -closed set.

Proof: Let A be a gT -closed set and $A \subseteq U$, U is open. Then $cl_{\mathcal{T}}(A) \subseteq U$, but $cl(A) \subseteq cl_{\mathcal{T}}(A)$ and then, $cl(A) \subseteq U$. Thus A is g -closed set.

The converse of the previous proposition is not true in general as shown from the following example.

Example 4.2 Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$, $\tau = \{X, \emptyset, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{b, c\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b, d\}\}$. We have $\{a, d\}$ is g -closed set but not gT -closed.

Proposition 4.4 Every θ - g -closed set is gT -closed.

Proof: Let A be a θ - g -closed set where $A \subseteq U$ and U is open. Then $cl_{\theta}(A) \subseteq U$. But $cl_{\mathcal{T}}(A) \subseteq cl_{\theta}(A)$, hence $cl_{\mathcal{T}}(A) \subseteq U$. Thus A is gT -closed.

The converse of the previous proposition is not true in general as shown from the following example.

Example 4.3 Let $X = \{a, b, c, d, e\}$, $\tau = \{X, \emptyset, \{a, b, c\}, \{c, d, e\}, \{c\}\}$. We have $\{a\}$ is gT -closed but not θ - g -closed.

From propositions 4.2, 4.3, and 4.4 the diagram in [2] can be extended to the following one.

Figure (2)

Proposition 4.4 If $A \subseteq X$ is gT -closed, then $cl_{\tau}(A) - A$ does not contain a non-empty closed set.

Proof: Let $F \subseteq cl_{\tau}(A) - A$ be a closed set. Then, $A \subseteq F^c$ and since A is gT -closed, we have $cl_{\tau}(A) \subseteq F^c$. Thus, $F \subseteq cl_{\tau}(A) \cap (cl_{\tau}(A))^c = \emptyset$ which means that F is empty.

Proposition 4.5 A subset A of a topological space X is gT -closed iff $A \equiv cl_{\tau}(A)$.

Proof. Let A be a gT -closed set. Then, $A \subseteq U$ iff $cl_{\tau}(A) \subseteq U$ where U is open. Thus, $A \equiv cl_{\tau}(A)$. Conversely, Let $A \equiv cl_{\tau}(A)$. Then, if $A \subseteq U$ and U is open implies $cl_{\tau}(A) \subseteq U$ and then A is gT -closed.

Proposition 4.6 The union of two gT -closed sets is gT -closed.

Proof: Let A, B be gT -closed sets and suppose that $A \cup B \subseteq U$ and U is open. Then $A \subseteq U$ and hence $cl_{\tau}(A) \subseteq U$ since A is gT -closed set. Similarly, $cl_{\tau}(B) \subseteq U$ and therefore, $cl_{\tau}(A \cup B) = cl_{\tau}(A) \cup cl_{\tau}(B) \subseteq U$. Thus $A \cup B$ is also gT -closed set.

The intersection of two gT -closed sets is not gT -closed in general as shown from the following example.

Example 4.3 Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$, $\tau = \{X, \emptyset, \{a\}\}$. The sets $\{a, b\}$ and $\{a, c\}$ are gT -closed sets but its intersection $\{a\}$ is not gT -closed set.

Proposition 4.6 The intersection of a gT -closed and a T -closed is always a gT -closed.

Proof: Let A be a gT -closed and let F be a T -closed. Suppose that $A \cap F \subseteq U$ where U is an open set. Putting $G = F^c$, then $A \subseteq U \cup G$. But since G is T -open and U is open, then $G \cup U$ is open set and hence $cl_{\tau}(A) \subseteq G \cup U$. Now, we can write $cl_{\tau}(A \cap F) \subseteq cl_{\tau}(A) \cap cl_{\tau}(F) = cl_{\tau}(A) \cap F \subseteq (G \cup U) \cap F = (G \cap F) \cup (U \cap F) = \emptyset \cup (U \cap F) \subseteq U$. Thus $A \cap F$ is a gT -closed set.

Proposition 4.7 A topological space X is a $T_{1/2}$ -space iff every gT -closed is closed.

Proof: Let X be a $T_{1/2}$ -space, and suppose that $A \subseteq X$ is a gT -closed set, then, A is g -closed and since X is $T_{1/2}$ -space hence, A is closed. Conversely, Let $x \in X$. If $\{x\}$ is not closed, then $\{x\}^c$ is not open and hence the only superset of $\{x\}^c$ is X . Thus, $\{x\}^c$ is gT -closed and hence closed from the assumption which means that $\{x\}$ is open. Thus, every singleton set is either open or closed and therefore, X is a $T_{1/2}$ -space.

5. APPLICATION OF T-CLOSED SETS.

In this section, we introduce new separation axioms called T_c -space, T_{θ} -space and we study its properties and its relation with $T_{1/2}$ -space which is considered as a main tool in digital Topology.

Definition 5.1 A topological space X is called T_c -space if every g -closed set is T -closed.

Definition 5.2 A topological space X is called T_{θ} -space if every T -closed set is θ -closed.

Proposition 5.1 Every T_c -space is $T_{1/2}$ -space.

Proof. Let X be T_c -space. Suppose that A is g -closed set and since X is T_c -space then, A is T -closed and hence closed. Therefore X is $T_{1/2}$ -space.

The converse of the previous proposition is not true in general as shown from the following example.

Example 5.1 Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$ and $\tau = \{X, \phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b, d\}\}$, then (X, τ) is a $T_{1/2}$ -space. But (X, τ) is not T_c -space since $\{c\}$ is g-closed set but not T-closed.

Proposition 5.2 Every $T_{1/2}$ -space is T_θ -space.

Proof. Let X be $T_{1/2}$ -space, then g-closed sets and closed sets coincide. Hence for any subset $A \subseteq X$, $cl(A) = cl^*(A)$. Therefore, θ -closed sets and T-closed sets coincide which means that X is T_θ -space.

The converse of the previous proposition is not true in general as shown from the following example.

Example 5.2 Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $\tau = \{X, \phi, \{a, c\}\}$. (X, τ) is T_θ -space but not $T_{1/2}$ -space, since $\{b\}$ is g-closed but not closed.

From the above propositions, we have the following implications

Figure (3)

These implications can't be reversed as we shown earlier.

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